

DEVELOPMENT OF A HYDRAULIC PISTON PRESS BIOMASS-BRIQUETTING MACHINE FOR PRODUCTION OF HOLLOW-BRIQUETTES

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture remains the main-stay of Nigeria's economy and the main occupation of most Nigerians, which involves a lot of activities that generate a large amount of wastes such as rice husk, stalks, corncob, bagasse etc. These wastes often pose serious disposal challenges to farmers and mostly disposed indiscriminately. And because of the waste's loosed bulk density, they burn inefficiently, releasing excessive amount of smoke into the atmosphere and inconvenient for domestic cooking. Converting agricultural waste into hollow-briquettes, will make them suitable for domestic cooking with little or no smoke compared to solid briquettes. A biomass hollow-briquette making machine was developed and tested. The machine consisted of a 5 tons' hydraulic jack, four piston rams attached to a movable lower compression plate, four fixed moulds, an upper compression plate and two helical springs. The machine was tested with three biomass materials – sorghum stalk, millet stalk and corncob, and performed satisfactorily except with corncob. And being a prototype, has a capacity of 20 briquettes per hour without any failure in all briquettes produced from sorghum and millet stalks. The machine is portable, easy to disassembled and reassembled.

KEYWORDS: biomass, hollow-briquette, agricultural waste and machine

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, the trend of growth in energy consumption is on the rise and it is expected to keep rising primarily because of the expected growth in the world population and economic growth of the developing countries. Edirin and Nosa (2012) reported that 85% of the world's energy demand is met by combustion of fossil fuels which are depletable and the global energy demand is expected to grow by about 50% by 2025 with the major part of this increase coming from rapidly emerging countries.

In Nigeria, the escalating cost of petroleum products and irregular electricity supply, makes fuel wood to become a major source of fuel for families and small to medium enterprises. However, the use of wood as a

fuel source comes with certain disadvantages: deforestation, climate change, soil erosion, desertification, and health problems as a result of exposure to carbon emission during indoor domestic cooking. There is the need to provide an alternative source of energy that will replace firewood. Hence, biomass conversions have been one of the focal areas of research and development as a sustainable substitute to firewood and depleting fuels.

Developing countries are known to produce large quantities of agricultural waste and residues. For example, Nigeria's total biomass potential consisting of animal and agricultural waste and wood residues was estimated to be 1.2×10^{15} J (Obioh and

Fagbenle, 2009). In 2005, research revealed that bio-energy reserves/potential of Nigeria stood at 13,071,464 hectares, 61 million tonnes per year, 83 million tonnes for fuel wood, animal waste and crop residues respectively (Agba et al., 2010). But these agricultural and forestry residues produced annually are vastly under-utilized. The common practice is to burn these residues or leave them to decompose causing extensive degradation to the environment (Jekayinfa and Omisakin, 2005). These residual materials, however, can be briquetted in order to optimize their use. One of the major ways to convert biomass into an efficient energy source is biomass densification otherwise known as briquetting (Ajieh et al., 2016).

Briquetting agricultural waste and residues requires briquetting machine. Research on briquetting techniques in Nigeria is still underway as many of the indigenous briquetting machines produces solid-briquettes which is characterized with poor combustion characteristics (Grover and Mishra, 1996). Adekoya (1989) developed a manual press briquetting machine that produced six solid briquette pieces at a time; Olorunnisola (2007) fabricated a manually operated closed-end piston press that produced circular solid briquettes; Oumarou and Oluwole (2010) designed a pedal operated briquette piston press for production of rectangular solid briquettes. In like manner, a piston press briquetting machine, capable of producing 35 pieces of rectangular solid briquette at a time was developed by Obi et al., (2013). Although research works have been carried out on production of hollow briquettes, but these hollow briquettes were produce using cumbersome machines in laboratories. This therefore, necessitates the development of simple briquetting machine for production of homemade, hollow briquettes with good

combustion property. The aim of the study is to develop a hydraulic piston press biomass hollow briquette making machine and to carry out tests to ascertain the performance of the machine using millet stalk and sorghum stalk.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Design Consideration

The machine was considered to be portable, detachable and easy to assemble components. The materials selection for the briquetting machine components was based on the size of the briquette, the type of force acting on the machine members, the environmental condition in which they function, cost and their availability in the local market. Also, briquette size will be suitable for use in conventional charcoal stoves.

1.2 Design Calculation

2.2.1 Briquette size

The briquette size is important in determining the machine's mould dimensions. For the circular hollow briquette, an outer diameter, inner diameter and height of 100mm, 25mm and 50mm respectively were chosen.

2.2.2 Determination of allowable tensile stress

According to Khurmi (2005) the allowable tensile stress (i.e. circumferential or hoop stress) is:

$$\hat{\sigma}_t = \frac{\text{Tensile strength of Mild Steel}}{\text{Factor of Safety}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{That is, } \sigma_c = \frac{450}{5} = 88\text{N/mm}^2$$

2.2.3 Determination of thickness of cylinder in machine mould

As a result of the internal pressure, the mould has the tendency to split into two troughs along its circumferential axis.

It is therefore necessary to determine the minimum thickness of the mould shell that will withstand the internal pressure during briquetting. According to Khurmi (2005);

$$t = \frac{P \cdot d}{2 \sigma_c \eta} \quad (2)$$

Where, t = thickness of shell (mm), P = internal pressure in cylinder (MPa), d = internal diameter of cylinder (mm)

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_c &= \text{allowable tensile stress (MPa)} \\ \eta &= \text{efficiency of riveted joint. (neglected)} \\ \therefore t &= (5 \times 102) / (2 \times 88) = 2.898 \text{ mm} \approx 3 \text{ mm} \\ & \text{(standard size)} \end{aligned}$$

2.2.3 Preliminary Laboratory Test

A preliminary laboratory test was carried out to determine the pressure developed in compacting loose biomass material into hollow-briquette of internal and outer diameters of 50 mm and 100 mm, respectively. The test results gave an average pressure of 6.25 MN/m².

$$\text{Recall: Briquetting Pressure, } p = \frac{F}{A} \quad (3)$$

Where, P = Pressure required to compact loose material into hollow briquette (MN/m)

F = Force required to compact loose material into hollow briquette (N)

A = Cross-sectional area of hollow briquette (m²)

Cross sectional area of hollow briquette,

$$A = \frac{\pi(D^2 - d^2)}{4}$$

Where, D = outer diameter of hollow briquette = 0.1m; d = internal diameter of hollow briquette = 0.05 m ..

Thus, $A = 5.89125 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$.

Then, the experimental force of compaction of loose biomass material into hollow briquette was found to be:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= P \times A = 6250000 \text{ N/m}^2 \times 5.89125 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \\ &= 36820.3 \text{ N} \end{aligned}$$

2.2.5 Determination of the Capacity of Compacting Device (Hydraulic Jack)

The capacity of the hydraulic jack used for the briquetting machine was designed using Nordiana (2009) procedures which include determination of the following:

The weight of the machine components to be lifted by the jack (i.e. lower compression plate and four pistons).

The weight of briquette in the mould

The force required for compacting the loose biomass in the mould into briquette.

2.2.5.1 Determination of the weight of lower compression plate

The lower compression plate is made up of mild steel of density 7850kg/m³. It has dimensions of 300 mm x 300 mm x 3 mm corresponding to length, width and thickness respectively. The weight of the lower compression plate was calculated using Equation 5 (Nordiana, 2009):

$$W_{lcp} = l \times w \times t \times \rho \times g \quad (5)$$

Where, W_{lcp} = Weight of lower compression plate (N), l = length of plate = 0.3m, w = width of plate = 0.3m, t = thickness of plate = 0.003m, ρ = density of mild steel = 7850kg/m³ and g = acceleration due to gravity = 9.81m/s².

$$W_{lcp} = 20.79 \text{ N}$$

2.2.5.1 Determination of weight of pistons

The piston has three (3) components; a small open cylinder to hold the detachable PVC pipe in position for creation of hollow space in briquette, a big hollow cylinder cover at both ends called the piston head, and a connecting pipe to the lower compression plate.

1. The small cylinder has an internal and outer diameter of 15.5mm and 20.5mm, respectively. The weight of this cylinder was calculated using Equation 6 (Adopted from Nordiana, 2009):

$$W_{sc} = \frac{\pi}{4} (d_o^2 - d_i^2) h \rho \quad (6)$$

Where, W_{sc} = weight of small cylinder (N), d_o = outer diameter of small cylinder = 0.0205 m, d_i = inner diameter of small cylinder = 0.0155 m, h = height of small cylinder = 0.02 m, π = 3.142.

$$W_{sc} = 0.22\text{N}$$

2. The piston head has an internal and outer diameter of 94 mm and 100 mm, respectively, the weight of the piston head was calculated using Equation 7

$$W_p = \frac{\pi}{4} (d_o^2 - d_i^2) h + 2d_h t \rho \quad (7)$$

Where, W_p = weight of piston head (N), d_o = outer diameter of big cylinder = 0.1 m, d_i = inner diameter of big cylinder = 0.094 m, h = height of piston head = 0.05 m, d_h = diameter of the circular head = 0.1 m, t = thickness of top and bottom plates = 0.003 m.

$$W_p = 39.81\text{ N}$$

3. The connecting pipe has an internal and outer diameter of 54 mm and 60 mm. The weight of the connecting cylinder was calculated using Equation 8

$$W_{cp} = \frac{\pi}{4} (d_o^2 - d_i^2) h \rho \quad (8)$$

Where, W_{cp} = weight of connecting pipe (N), d_o = outer diameter of connecting cylinder = 0.060 m, d_i = inner diameter of big cylinder = 0.054 m, h = 0.1 m.

$$W_{cp} = 4.14\text{ N}$$

Thus, the weight of a piston,

$$W = W_{sc} + W_p + W_{cp} = 0.22\text{ N} + 39.81\text{ N} + 4.14\text{ N} = 44.17\text{ N}.$$

The total weight of four (4)

$$\text{piston rams} = 41.17\text{ N} \times 4 = 176.68\text{ N}$$

2.2.5.3 Determination of weight of briquettes

From the laboratory test, the average mass of briquette produced was found to be = 0.44 kg, Hence, the weight of briquette = 0.44 kg x 9.81 m/s² = 4.32 N

$$\text{The total weight of four briquettes} = 4.32\text{ N} \times 4 = 17.27\text{ N}$$

And, the total weight to be lifted by the hydraulic jack is = 17.27 N + 176.68 N + 20.79 N

$$= 214.74\text{N}$$

2.2.5.4 Determination of force for compaction

Hence, the total force required for the hydraulic jack to overcome the weight of machine components, briquette weights and to successfully compact stalk materials into briquette was estimated to be:

= force

$$36820.3\text{ N} + 214.74\text{ N} = 37\ 035.04\text{ N}.$$

Therefore, the minimum capacity of the hydraulic jack was:

$$= \frac{37035.04}{9.81} = 3775.2\text{ kg} \approx 4\text{ tons}$$

2.3 Machine Evaluation

The performance of the hollow-briquette making machine was tested using dried corncob, millet and sorghum stalks which are readily available in semi-arid and arid zones (Sokoto, Yobe, Borno, Jigawa and Kano) of Nigeria that are faced with desertification, due to deforestation activities of the dwellers, mostly for domestic cooking purposes. The corncob, millet and sorghum stalks were collected

from Samaru College of Agriculture farm lands. The plant materials were crushed using hammer mill with screen size opening of 3mm. Cassava starch was used as a binding agent mainly to enhance the compaction and to overcome the post-compaction recovery of the loose biomass materials.

The machine output capacity was determined according to Obi et al. (2013) as the ratio of the mass of total briquettes, in kg, in a single production by the biomass hollow-briquette making machine to the average time used in production of the briquette. That is:

$$\text{Machine output capacity (kg/s)} = \frac{\text{mass to total briquette in a single production (kg)}}{\text{briquettes production time (kg)}}$$

2.4 Construction of Hollow-Briquette Making Machine

The hollow briquette making machine consists of upper compression plate, mould, pistons, lower compression plate and the machine stand (support); operated by a 5-ton hydraulic jack (See Figure 1).

Upper Compression Plate: The upper compression plate is made of mild steel plate. It is a square plate with length and thickness of 300 mm x 5 mm respectively. Four holes of diameter 28 mm were drilled at the top of the plate, arranged in two columns, two rows and equidistant from the edges of the plate, for free passage of the removable PVC pipes during compaction, which runs from the top of the pistons in the machine mould and creates the hollow space in the briquette. The Plate is hinged to the machine mould at one end. The other end and sides of the plate were provided with bolts and nuts to fasten the upper compression plate to the machine mould before compaction.

Mould: The machine mould consists of four cylindrical pipes and two square plates. The plates are made of mild steels having length and thickness of 300 mm x 3 mm respectively while the cylindrical pipes are made of galvanized steel with outer diameter, inner diameter and height of 116 mm x 102 mm x 150 mm respectively. The cylindrical pipes were arranged in two columns and two rows. One plate was engineered at the top of the pipes and the other at the bottom. The cylindrical pipes were made to be open at both ends.

Pistons: The piston assembly consists of a cylindrical ram and a piston rod (or connecting rod). The cylinder ram is hollow cylinder of outer diameter, 100 mm and height, 50 mm which closed at both ends. A cylindrical pipe of diameter 26 mm and height 15 mm was welded to the top-centre of the ram cylinder to provide grip for the removable PVC. Then the connecting rod of 50 mm diameter and 120 mm height was welded to the bottom of the ram cylinder.

Lower Compression Plate: The lower compression plate is square plate of length 300 mm and thickness 5 mm, made of mild steel. Four pistons arranged in two columns and two rows were welded to the plate. Its purpose is to convey the pistons in the mould, from its bottom dead centre (BDC) to its top dead centre (TDC), to and fro – during and after compaction. It receives its drive from the 5-ton hydraulic jack.

Figure 1. Constructed Briquetting Machine

A – Upper compression plate; B – Mould; C – Piston (Connecting rod); D – Lower compression plate; E – Cylindrical pipe; F – Jack seat plate; G – Jack head plate; H – 5 tons' hydraulic jack; I – Iron rod

Machine Stand: The machine stand consists of jack head plate, iron rod, cylindrical pipe, and the jack seat plate. The

jack head plate is a square, made of mild steel plate having length and thickness of 300 mm x 5 mm respectively. At its centre was drilled a hole of diameter 30 mm in order to allow free passage of the hydraulic jack piston. Also, the jack head plate serves as a resting point for the lower compression plate (Figure). The iron rod is of length 389mm and diameter 18.34 mm. One rod was welded to each corner of the jack set plate at one end, the other end of the rod was threaded in which the mould is bolted and the lower compression plate travels up and down the exposed length of the iron rod. The cylindrical pipe has a length of 400 mm. It housed and provide support for the iron rod and serves as a stopper for jack head plate and the lower compression plate. The jack seat plate is similar to the jack head plate in dimensions with exception of the centre hole, on which the hydraulic jack is placed for its operation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Machine Output Capacity

The result of the briquetting machine output capacity was estimated based on the mass of the ejected briquettes and the average time taken to produce briquette presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Table of values of Briquetting Test

S/N	Biomass materials	No. of Briquettes produced in 3 operations	No. of broken briquettes produced in 3 operations	Average Mass of Briquettes per operation (g)	Average time of briquetting per operation (s)	Machine output capacity (kg/hr)
1.	Sorghum stalk	12	Nil	888.72	693	4.64
2.	Millet stalk	12	Nil	997.58	693	5.20
3.	Corn cob	12	9	758.27	693	3.95

The result of the test (Table 1) showed that the machine performed excellently while briquetting sorghum and millet particles, with unbroken briquettes from the 12 briquettes produced from these materials in three operations. But the machine performed poorly in briquetting corncob particle (see Figure 2), which is suspected that the particle size of corncob at 3mm

may be too high and compacting pressure (at experimental value of 6.25MPa) may be low to achieve successful compaction of corncob particles into hollow briquette by the machine constructed. Olajide and Enweremadu (2012) reported that corncob briquettes exhibited most positive attributes at processing parameters of 0.60mm and 6.6MPa for particle size and compacting pressure respectively.

Figure 2: Examples of Hollow-Briquettes Produced From: A- Sorghum straws, B – Millet straws and C – Corn straws; Using The Constructed Briquetting Machine.

Also, the machine was operated at an average time of 693 seconds which is equivalent to 11.53 minutes per production. A mean loading time, compaction time, residence time and ejection time of 12s, 58s, 600s and 23s respectively. The machine output capacity was found to vary with biomass material type as shown in Table 1. The output capacity ranged from 3.95–5.20 kg/hr considering the fact that the biomass materials are light materials. The output capacity of the developed hollow briquette making machine is lower compared to the briquetting capacity of the machine developed by Sani (2008), Nordiana (2009) and Obi *et al.* (2013). This is because the number of mould and subsequently the number of briquettes produced per time by the developed hollow

briquette making machine, which is four is small compared to that of Sani (2008), Nordiana (2009) and Obi *et al.* (2013) with 10 moulds, 9 moulds and 36 moulds respectively. But the developed hollow briquette making machine has an advantage of simplicity, portability and low cost compared to existing local briquetting machines.

4. DESIGN LIMITATIONS

In operation, the machine was observed to experience buckling which was not considered in the machine design. This eventually limited the possible compacting pressure that could be developed by the machine in operation because the more the pressure used in compaction the more the machine buckled (See Figure 2 in Appendix).

5. CONCLUSION

A portable briquetting machine suitable for homemade briquetting of farm wastes was produced and used to produce hollow-circular briquettes which are suitable for indoor domestic cooking. The machine is capable of producing good briquette from sorghum and millet biomass particle at 3 mm particle size. The briquettes when burnt, burnt with blue flame with little or no smoke which signified complete combustion as a result of the hole at the centre of the briquette and thus, suitable for indoor cooking.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Briquetting procedure before ejection of briquette from the machine

